

A Comprehensive Survey of Manual and Dynamic Approaches for Cybersecurity Taxonomy Generation

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Abstract

The aim of this work is to provide a systematic literature review of techniques for taxonomy generation across the cybersecurity domain. Cybersecurity taxonomies can be classified into manual and dynamic, each one of which focuses on different characteristics and tails different goals. Under this premise, we investigate the current state of the art in both categories with respect to their characteristics, applications and methods. To this end, we perform a systematic literature review in accordance with an extensive analysis of the tremendous need for dynamic taxonomies in the cybersecurity landscape. This analysis provides key insights into the advantages and limitations of both techniques, and it discusses the datasets which are most commonly used to generate cybersecurity taxonomies.

Keywords: cybersecurity, taxonomy, manual taxonomy, dynamic taxonomy, cybersecurity datasets

1 Introduction

The landscape of cyber attacks is constantly evolving as the effort required to perform such acts decreases over time. In the last decade, well-resourced threat actors have had ease of access to several tactics, techniques and procedures to conduct cybersecurity attacks [1, 2]. Within this context, the development and implementation of robust taxonomy frameworks play a crucial role in organising knowledge, facilitating communication, and guiding research. In this sense, cybersecurity taxonomies can serve as a hierarchical structure to analyse categories, subcategories, and relationships between cybersecurity threats and incidents. They can also be leveraged to assess security incidents, events, and response procedures [3-6].

This paper provides a comprehensive review of the existing literature on cybersecurity taxonomy methodologies, with a particular focus on adopting a threat-oriented perspective in its analysis of cybersecurity. Considering that the term taxonomy is often but erroneously confused in the literature with the term classification, we should highlight a key difference between cybersecurity taxonomies and threat classification techniques. While both terms are often used interchangeably, they are characterised by distinct differences. The former refers to a broad framework for categorising and organising knowledge within the cybersecurity domain. Therefore, it formulates a holistic view of the landscape and aspires to map out the entire field and its interconnected elements. The latter refers to the identification and classification of specific elements of cybersecurity, including threat types, or groups of threats. In contrast to existing surveys that focus on the classification of cyber threats, this study approaches the techniques which are used to construct the cybersecurity taxonomies themselves.

In this context, the study identifies a significant gap in the approaches used for constructing cybersecurity taxonomies. In particular, there is a large disparity between the number of taxonomies created through the cognitive efforts of human domain experts, referred to here as *manual* taxonomies, and the number of taxonomies constructed employing automated or semi-automated techniques, referred to as *dynamic* taxonomies.

We highlight the current lack of research approaches towards enabling the implementation of dynamic taxonomies within the cybersecurity domain, despite the improvements such approaches could offer in terms of efficiency, speed, scalability, and adaptability in managing cyber threats, and the proliferation of Machine Learning (ML)-driven approaches that facilitate automation. Potential reasons for the lack of approaches for constructing dynamic taxonomies include the data dependency of current automation methods and the necessity of human-level contextual understanding (in addition to any (semi)-automated techniques) to create taxonomies suitable for practical use.

Overall, in this study we review and organize previous works on cybersecurity taxonomy creation; this categorisation yields two distinct categories: manual and dynamic. Using this distinction we assess the studies conducted in each category and we present the datasets which are often used for taxonomy generation. Additionally, we provide a comparison, based on existing literature, between those two methods. The key contributions of this study are:

- To the best of our knowledge, there is no other work that performs a wide study on the field of taxonomy generation concerning the cybersecurity domain including dynamic taxonomies. We consider this study to be the first to attempt to classify and organise previous works on the cybersecurity taxonomy generation domain that involve automated or semi-automated techniques.

- We provide a quantitative and qualitative analysis of the papers produced so far in the aforementioned domain by highlighting statistical information and grouping them according to the methods they employ.
- We extract useful information from the datasets employed for taxonomy generation, which can act as guidance for future research endeavours.
- We provide insights into the strengths and weaknesses of the manual and dynamic taxonomies and thus, we pave the road towards targeted research activities to alleviate the disadvantages of both techniques.

Furthermore, this work can have a significant impact on policies as well as the private and public sectors as it is multifaceted and shows great potential for practical implementation. In particular, the potential contribution of the proposed methodologies concerning dynamic taxonomies and remediation methodologies pertains to an increase in the efficiency of operations by decreasing the overall cost of managing cybersecurity. This is achieved by optimising processes for threat identification, evaluation, and mitigation that considerably reduce the time and workforce required. The implications of the research are well-aligned with contemporary legislative and regulatory imperatives, such as the NIS2 Directive¹ of the European Union. The directive identifies the importance of CTI towards achieving the objectives of the NIS2 Directive as well as the use of taxonomies, to enhance cybersecurity frameworks across critical infrastructure sectors. These taxonomies when put into practice will greatly facilitate a more coordinated and uniform approach to the categorisation and reporting of threats, allowing policymakers to develop informed strategies for mitigating risk at both the national and international levels.

The paper is organised as follows. In 2 we discuss the method we used to perform our study and we pose our research questions. In Section 3 we present the literature survey and we assess the research landscape of the taxonomy generation domain. In

¹<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2022/2555>

Section 4 we report on the open issues and research opportunities which are opened through this work and conclude this paper.

2 Research Methodology

In this work, we assess the scientific literature on techniques for cybersecurity taxonomies, with a specific focus on the separation between manual and dynamic techniques. To accomplish this, we follow the methodology described in this section to locate and select studies which are related to this topic. Specifically, the implemented methodology leverages some features of PRISMA statement² as well as inductive research approach³. Concerning PRISMA, it provides evidence-based guidance for the reporting of systematic reviews evaluating the effects of interventions. The methodology that is followed in this work leverages parts of the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram⁴, PRISMA 2020 checklist⁵ and specific guidelines according to the PRISMA 2020 explanation and elaboration updated guidance [7]. On the other hand, the inductive approach, also known as inductive reasoning, starts with observations and moves to the formulation of theories that stem from the observation. Inductive research involves the identification of patterns in the data, and developing explanations or theories through the iterative generation of hypotheses [8]. Nevertheless, the inductive approach allows for the formulation of research with the main focus of identifying and deriving relationships from data collected to identify patterns and relationships that can contribute towards answering the research questions. Furthermore, the implemented methodology adopts some features from other survey papers that also leverage parts of the PRISMA statement [3, 9, 10]. Consequently, our methodology follows a structured

²<https://www.prisma-statement.org/>

³<https://research-methodology.net/research-methodology/research-approach/inductive-approach-2/>

⁴<https://www.prisma-statement.org/prisma-2020-flow-diagram>

⁵<https://www.prisma-statement.org/prisma-2020-checklist>

process of five distinct phases concerning the assessment and selection of appropriate studies for this survey. In this regard, the following research questions have been defined to guide the research methodology.

- **RQ1:** What are the existing methodologies for generating cybersecurity taxonomies?
- **RQ2:** How do Artificial Intelligence (AI) and ML approaches improve the generation of cybersecurity taxonomies?
- **RQ3:** What are the comparative advantages and limitations of taxonomy creation in a dynamic versus manual manner within the cybersecurity domain?

In order to assess each identified research paper in terms of its relevance to the target scope of this work, we employed the four key steps of PRISMA along with a snowballing phase prior to the Inclusion phase. Specifically, the implemented methodology consists of five sequential phases, namely, i) Identification, ii) Screening, iii) Eligibility, vi) Snowballing and v) Inclusion. Each phase includes assessment steps which might result in the exclusion of several studies (i.e., research papers) in case they don't meet the inclusion criteria. Figure 1 depicts the implemented research methodology. The PRISMA flow diagram was employed to document the progression of studies through the key stages: identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion. A comprehensive search strategy was implemented across well-known and peer-reviewed databases, resulting in 412 records.

Initially, during the *Identification* phase, we identify a set of keywords which are directly related to either dynamic or manual methods, as well as cybersecurity taxonomies. The final set includes:

- Machine learning cybersecurity taxonomies
- Artificial intelligence cybersecurity taxonomies
- Cybersecurity taxonomies
- Cyber threat taxonomies

- Taxonomy generation for cybersecurity
- KeyTerm Extraction for cybersecurity taxonomy generation
- Pattern-based methods for cybersecurity taxonomy generation
- Distributional methods for cybersecurity taxonomy generation
- Supervised Models for cybersecurity taxonomy generation
- Taxonomy induction for cybersecurity taxonomy generation
- Incremental Learning for cybersecurity taxonomy generation General
- Clustering for cybersecurity taxonomy generation
- Graph-Based Induction for cybersecurity taxonomy generation
- NER for cybersecurity taxonomy generation
- Topic modeling for cybersecurity taxonomy generation.

Subsequently, the keywords have been queried against well-known and peer-reviewed databases including publisher-specific repositories such as IEEE Xplore⁶, ACM Digital Library⁷, SpringerLink⁸ and Science Direct⁹ as well as search engines such as Google Scholar¹⁰. Furthermore, we also filter out works which are published in a period longer than seven years (i.e., 2017 - 2024), duplicates and research papers which are not written in English. The selection of works ranges between 2017 and 2024, considering that this period reflects the new developments in taxonomy design, classification frameworks, and a variety of evaluation methods being proposed to keep pace with new challenges through real-time threat intelligence. As for the research on recent publications, it will ensure the relevance of current cybersecurity practices, regulatory contexts, and technological innovations; thus, such a study provides updated insights into developing and applying effective taxonomies against the current evolving cyber threats.

⁶<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xplore/home.jsp>

⁷<https://dl.acm.org>

⁸<https://link.springer.com>

⁹<https://www.sciencedirect.com>

¹⁰<https://> and academic search engines such as scholar.google.com

During the second phase, the resulting studies have been subjected to *Screening* based on their title and abstract. In particular, each research paper has been reviewed to identify research papers that are not relevant based on their title and keywords. The research papers that have been deemed relevant were subsequently reviewed in terms of the contents of their abstract. Following the title and abstract screening, the studies are further assessed based on their introduction and conclusions section where those that are considered irrelevant are excluded resulting in a reduced amount of studies.

With regard to the *Eligibility* phase, the research papers that have successfully passed the *Screening* phase are carefully studied concerning the ability to answer any of the research questions that have been defined earlier in this work. Specifically, each research paper undergoes a full-text review to determine the aspects that they are addressing. The studies that do not address the techniques used for generating cybersecurity taxonomies (either manual or dynamic), are deemed irrelevant and are excluded from the set of research papers.

The next phase of the research methodology is *Snowballing* where we leverage the snowballing approach to find additional studies, leveraging the research papers that passed the *Eligibility* phase as the start set. The snowballing methodology adopted in this study follows the guidelines of implementing snowballing in systematic literature studies, as described in relevant works in the literature [11]. According to the authors in [11], snowballing is a systematic process of identification of relevant studies by backward and forward searching for references. This is to complement conventional database searches and ensure complete literature coverage by identifying studies that may not be indexed in commonly used databases. Through the snowballing method, new papers are discovered based on the reference list as well as the citation list of the research paper. Thus, we expand our paper catalogue by consulting the references of the research paper under examination. During this phase, we implement both backwards and forward snowballing for each paper. In particular, in backward snowballing,

we examine the reference list to identify new papers while in forward snowballing we identify new papers based on those papers citing the paper being examined. Each identified paper is subjected to the 7-year period filtering (i.e., snowballing stop criteria), and subsequently the same assessment process as the initial set of studies. Concerning the 7-year period filtering, exceptions were made only for specific studies that describe fundamental concepts and methodologies.

Finally, the *Inclusion* phase includes the final set of research papers that have been used to conduct the survey in this work. The final set consists of the papers from the *Eligibility* phase including papers from both the initial set and the *Snowballing* phase.

3 Existing Taxonomies Targeted to Cybersecurity

In this section, we discuss the findings of our research providing detailed information about manual and dynamic cybersecurity taxonomies, datasets for building cybersecurity taxonomies and an in-depth evaluation of the advantages and drawbacks of dynamic taxonomies compared to manual taxonomies. This section directly answers the three main research questions of the paper namely RQ1 is answered in 3.3, RQ2 is answered in 3.3.2 and 3.5.1, while RQ3 is answered in 3.5. First, we present a quick definition of what a taxonomy is and then we argue on the added value it provides in the cybersecurity domain. We proceed to present prominent taxonomy datasets and we analyse the existing literature landscape of the dynamic and manual taxonomy methodologies. In the sequel, we provide an assessment of several datasets that are frequently leveraged by researchers for cybersecurity taxonomy generation. Finally, we perform a comparison between manual and dynamic taxonomy methods.

Fig. 1 The research methodology that has been implemented in this work towards identifying and evaluating the available literature.

3.1 Definition of taxonomies

Taxonomy originates from the Greek terms 'taxis', signifying 'arrangement', and 'nomos', meaning 'law' [12, 13]. It is a scientific discipline with the objective of systematically identifying, naming, illustrating, detailing, and categorising living entities according to a specific set of traits to simplify the process of recognition.

The concept of taxonomies is common in life sciences, botany as well as zoology [14], where taxonomies are used to classify plants and animals. A taxonomy can be described as a hierarchical organisation of knowledge with respect to specific attributes. Specifically, taxonomies represent a systematic methodology for classifying, naming, detailing, and identifying elements [12]. Generally, the definition of taxonomy requires identifying terms (i.e., entities), concepts (i.e., categories or classes), and hierarchical relations (taxonomic-relations) to build the hierarchy of concepts [15]. Taxonomies are crucial for both the theoretical and practical aspects of science, helping to structure existing knowledge and guide its progression. Considering the foundational concepts of taxonomy within the realms of physical sciences, content management, and information architecture can shed light on its relevance to the study and implications of cybersecurity.

3.2 Use of taxonomies in cybersecurity domain

With regard to the cybersecurity domain, taxonomies are considered paramount since they provide a systematic framework for the identification, classification, and management of cyber threats, vulnerabilities as well as other relevant aspects. Within the cybersecurity context, there are several taxonomies, each one of which selects different characteristics and pursues different goals [16]. Establishing and leveraging comprehensive cybersecurity taxonomies enables organisations to delineate and assess the landscape of cybersecurity risks, thereby facilitating a more informed and

strategic approach to threat mitigation. Furthermore, taxonomies assist in the categorisation of expertise within the cybersecurity field, as evidenced by the European proposal for a cybersecurity taxonomy [6], which aids in mapping the domains of expertise of EU cybersecurity centres. Additionally, a well-defined risk taxonomy is pivotal for understanding the vectors of cyber risk, enhancing communication with relevant stakeholders, and advocating for the necessary resources to facilitate and enhance the protection of the organisation. Consequently, the clarity and structure offered by taxonomies are critical in enabling swift and effective responses to cyber threats, underscoring their significance in the continual effort to safeguard digital infrastructures. Overall, taxonomies have played an important role in organising and understanding the cybersecurity ecosystem.

NIST's National Vulnerability Database (NVD) [17] is one of the most prominent databases which organises cybersecurity activities into various categories and subcategories such as security checklists, software vulnerabilities and impact metrics. In this sense, NVD is a cybersecurity taxonomy that encapsulates other, smaller taxonomies into a larger group. Mitre's Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE) [18] is another well-established taxonomy, which organises vulnerabilities found in software. This taxonomy includes software weaknesses such as low encryption strength, SQL injection, cross-site scripting (XSS) and buffer overflow, and provides a description for each one of them, accompanied by recommendations for mitigation measures. Taxonomies for attack types are also used, such as Mitre's Common Attack Patterns Enumerations and Characteristics (CAPEC) [19], which organises attack patterns into different categories. Attack tactics and techniques are considered in Mitre's Adversarial Tactics, Techniques and Common Knowledge (ATT&CK) [20] in which data are collected through real-world observations.

3.3 Taxonomy generation methodologies

For the purposes of this work, taxonomies created through the cognitive efforts of human domain experts, such as cybersecurity professionals, researchers, boards of experts, and consortia, are hereafter referred to as *manual* taxonomies, whereas taxonomies constructed using automated or semi-automated techniques are referred to as *dynamic* taxonomies. These terms are used throughout the paper.

The process of creating a manual taxonomy involves domain examination and analysis (e.g., analysis of threat reports, existing taxonomies, and relevant scientific literature), followed by the creation and introduction of a taxonomy, potentially along with methods of applying the taxonomy [21–24]. In terms of specific tasks, taxonomy creation involves identifying and defining concepts, identifying terms, and grouping and categorising concepts (defining the taxonomical relationships).

3.3.1 Manual Taxonomies

In terms of research, previous works focus on either introducing new taxonomies or modifying existing ones to fit different cybersecurity needs. Over the course of the last few decades, a significant number of manual, expert-driven taxonomies have been constructed for the domain of cybersecurity to address these needs. As a foundational step, "Howard's taxonomy" laid the foundation for modern cybersecurity categorization by introducing a structure for describing computer security incidents based on their features and impact [25]. Subsequently, the work of Hansman and Hunt proposed four dimensions, or "classifiers", for attack classification; attack vector, target, vulnerability, and payload [26], and Meyers, et al. proposed a similar taxonomy presenting nine classes of cyber attacks [27]. The AVOIDIT taxonomy classified attacks by five classifiers: attack vector, operational impact, defence, informational impact, and target [28]. ADAPT, a taxonomy based on a game theoretic approach, proposed

three classifiers: attacker, defender, and performance [29]. ADMIT employed five classifiers: attack vector, defence, method, impact, and attack target [30]. While these are among the most notable works, there are additional cybersecurity taxonomies. A comprehensive review of earlier taxonomies falls outside the scope of this study.

These contemporary taxonomies demonstrate a high level of thematical specialisation. The majority focus on either i) a specific IT-cybersecurity domain, for example, vehicular IoT [21, 31–33], and industrial IoT [24, 34–37], ii) a specific type of attack, for example, DDoS [38], or iii) cross-domain attacks [6].

Furthermore, the taxonomies might focus on cybersecurity in specific industries, such as Power Grid [38–40], the maritime sector [41] or the oil and gas sector [42], while others revolve around cybercrime and cyber-harm [12, 43–47], even a Covid-19-related cybersecurity attacks taxonomy [48] was created. The diversity in the established scopes and methodologies that are employed in the creation of the taxonomies, contributes to their non-homogeneity. There is a prominent lack of uniformity across the different cybersecurity taxonomies, and they vary significantly in terms of categorisation criteria, terminology, and structure.

Among the recently introduced approaches (i.e., 2017 - 2024) for taxonomies in the cybersecurity domain, some employ frameworks that aim to accommodate the whole spectrum of attacks and incidents [22, 49–52], but overall, their number is significantly smaller than that of the more specialised ones. The shortage of general cyber security taxonomies has also been noted in [4] and [53], potentially stemming from the difficulty of manually processing the vast, multidisciplinary, and rapidly evolving domain of cybersecurity [4].

We have classified the studies regarding manual taxonomies into nine categories. The categorisation of each study has been done according to the methodology as well as the target domain of the proposed taxonomy. The identified categories along with the relevant description and studies are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Cybersecurity taxonomy methodologies.

Taxonomy	Description	References
Based on the CIA triad	Taxonomies based on the Confidentiality Integrity Availability (CIA) triad.	[48]
Cyber Kill Chain based	Taxonomies based on Cyber Kill Chain concept.	[22, 49, 54–56]
Domain-specific	Taxonomies of cyber-attacks targeting specific domains such as Power Grid.	[21, 24, 34, 36, 38–40, 42, 55, 57–70]
Functionality-specific	Taxonomies of cyber-attacks targeting a specific functionality of a system such as ML.	[71, 72]
Attack-specific	Taxonomies of specific cyber-attacks such as DDoS.	[38, 39, 64, 67, 73–77]
Hybrid	Taxonomies that combine more than one criteria to classify an attack.	[3, 6, 24, 46, 48, 58, 60, 61, 78–81]
Affected layer	Taxonomies that classify threats according to the affected layer of the system, namely, hardware, software and network.	[12, 38, 42, 63, 65, 81–84]
Cross-domain	Taxonomies that help identify and detect cross-domain attacks.	[3, 4, 6, 22, 23, 34, 49, 50, 79, 84–89]
STRIDE Threat Schema	Taxonomy that leverage STRIDE threat classification model. This model categorises attacks into six types: Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service (DoS), and Elevation of Privilege.	[90]

Categorisation of manual cybersecurity taxonomies across the literature.

Considering the contents of Table 1 it is apparent that some studies are included in more than one category. In particular, several studies follow specific methodology (e.g., Cyber Kill Chain) while also addressing different domains (i.e., cross-domain). The column chart in Figure 2 presents the distribution of manual taxonomy studies per category. The rows and columns of the matrix associated with the chart correspond to the taxonomies of Table 1. The columns of each row are filled in according to the following methodology:

- In case the current reference in the category x (i.e., row) is identified in another category y (i.e., column) then the value of the column of this category y is increased by 1).
- In case the current reference in the category x (i.e., row) is **not** identified in another category y (i.e., column), then the value of the column of this category x is increased by 1).

- In case the current reference in the category x (i.e., row) is identified in two more categories y and z , then the value of each column of these categories y and z is increased by 0,5).

Fig. 2 Manual taxonomy studies per category.

In [91] authors introduce the concept of motivation-based cybersecurity taxonomy, where the motivations of malicious actors are taken into account and the organisation of knowledge is centred around this aspect. This approach can be used to assess the attack intensity, to narrow down cyber targets and to describe threat and risk scenarios in non-technical terms properly. This type of taxonomy creates 18 categories of agents, based on their behavioural motivations, such as considers civil activists, competitors, corrupt officials, data miners, employees, spies, legal adversaries, terrorists, thieves, vendors and others. A more structured approach towards agent-based taxonomy can be found in the Threat Agent Library (TAL) in [92]. Another approach in [93] catalogues software vulnerabilities and provides a taxonomy based on their common

identifiers. This classification scheme is a collection of publicly disclosed cybersecurity vulnerabilities and provides a standardised reference for each one.

3.3.2 Dynamic taxonomies

The increasing availability and diversity of accessible data necessitate the dynamic expansion of existing taxonomies. Without regular updates, they risk failing to capture emerging knowledge and becoming outdated. Given the volume and heterogeneity of available data, manual classification and organisation are obviously no longer feasible. Although the creation of taxonomies entails interpreting and classifying data within a specific context, which requires a lot of cognitive effort, the underlying semantics of taxonomies can be interpreted by machines. This indicates that the process of constructing and updating them could in principle be automated; systems that integrate ML can process vast amounts of data efficiently, making them invaluable for tasks such as classification and taxonomy generation. In the general domain, dynamic taxonomies are already widely used by online retailers and search engines to enhance product recommendations and improve query understanding [94, 95].

General domain approaches for dynamic taxonomies proposed in recent years [94–96], for taxonomy creation and expansion, are usually based on Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques such as text embeddings and neural language models and all of them process textual data. Despite the introduction of automation, these approaches also normally assume the contribution of a human during the overall process of the creation of a taxonomy.

In the case of the cybersecurity domain, during the examined timeframe (2017–2024), the very small number of dynamic approaches that have been proposed are primarily based on ML and Deep Learning (DL) techniques. Methods such as K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Decision Trees, Neural Networks, and NLP have been employed in efforts to classify cybersecurity-related data within a given frame of reference.

A semi-automated procedure for taxonomies generation was presented [4] utilising NLP and Information Retrieval (IR) tools such as TF-IDF and Document Count (DC) combined with human expertise to build and evaluate the generated taxonomies. The taxonomy procedure consists of three development stages: i) data collection, ii) text analysis, and iii) taxonomy generation. The automated tools were utilised during the text analysis procedure where human involvement was on all three development stages. The authors used different cybersecurity-related classes such as threat, attack and vulnerability and populated them with terms extracted during the taxonomy construction phase. A taxonomy for detecting DDoS attacks over Transport Layer protocols (i.e., TCP, UDP) called TaxoDaCML [73] entailed 11 classes of DDoS attacks such as LDAP, NetBios and DNS. KNNs and Decision Trees (DT) along with Neural Networks (NNs) were used during the taxonomy construction. The approach used reached 99.9% accuracy in DDoS attack detection and more than 85% in DDoS attack classification. The researchers in [97] developed a taxonomy to categorise cybersecurity datasets. They used 965 research papers published between 2012 and 2016. NLP, and ML, techniques were used to distinguish between dataset-related and non-dataset-related papers. The researchers employed text analysis tools such as Textblob to prepare the best papers used for analysis. Among the different models (i.e., Multinomial Naive Bayes, Bernoulli Naive Bayes, Gaussian Naïve Bayes, SVC Confusion Matrix, and Random Forest), Random forest achieved the best results. Authors in [77] propose a new DDoS attack taxonomy. This taxonomy entailed many categories and subcategories of DDoS attacks and was dependent on the type of vectors and techniques used in attacks and the nature of the attacks. Different ML algorithms including the ID3, the Random Forest, the Naïve Bayes, and the Logistic Regression were used during the taxonomy generation procedure. The algorithms were used to automatically identify the principal features of the data that relate them to the various techniques of DDoS attacks. ID3 was the best algorithm with the shortest execution

time and highest accuracy. The authors in [98] presented an end-to-end framework for taxonomy generation and updating utilizing the STIX 2.1 specification. Specifically, different methods for taxonomy creation were utilized such as NER and regex patterns. Newly built taxonomies along with existing open-sourced taxonomies were updated using the semantic search technique.

Table 2 highlights the distribution of taxonomies, showcasing the number of manual and dynamic taxonomies examined in this work. It is evident from the data that dynamic taxonomies are significantly fewer, with their count being approximately 10 times lower than that of manual taxonomies.

Table 2 Manual and dynamic taxonomies.

Taxonomy Type	Number of Studies	References
Manual	51	[3, 6, 12, 21–24, 34, 36, 38–40, 42, 46, 48–50, 54–72, 74–76, 79–90]
Dynamic	5	[4, 73, 77, 97, 98]

Distribution of manual and dynamic taxonomies.

3.4 Datasets for cybersecurity taxonomies

A significant amount of data is required to properly generate a cybersecurity taxonomy. The collection and analysis of such data is not a trivial part, and for this reason, pre-existing data catalogues are frequently used for such tasks. The datasets used for composing cybersecurity taxonomies described in section 3.3.2 are compiled in Table 3. According to the values in the table, two distinct types of datasets are evident, based on the type of data they contain; the DDoS datasets, consisting of network flows, and the cybersecurity-related texts datasets.

DDoS datasets (i.e., network flow datasets) that were described in these approaches are the 2000 DARPA Intrusion Detection Scenario dataset [99], the CAIDA UCSD "DDoS Attack 2007" dataset [100], and the CIC-DDoS2019 dataset [77]. The DARPA

2000 dataset contains three distinct subsets, each representing a different attack scenario, generated from the Wisconsin Re-Think meeting and the July 2000 Hawaii PI meeting [99]. These subsets include LLDOS 1.0 and LLDOS 2.0.2, both featuring DDoS attacks by novice attackers against naive defenders and a Windows NT Attack Data Set, which captures one day’s NT auditing and attack traffic by a novice attacker [99], [77]. The CAIDA “DDoS Attack 2007” Dataset includes one hour of anonymised traffic traces in PCAP format, detailing both attack traffic and victim responses [100], [77]. However, anonymisation can also be considered a drawback since it leads to loss of information. CIC-DDoS2019 is a DDoS dataset created to address the limitations of earlier datasets, such as the anonymisation of traffic, payload removal, and the absence of modern reflective DDoS attacks. It is fully labelled with 80 network traffic features and enables the identification of 13 different types (classes) of DDoS attacks, including reflective DDoS [77]. All three datasets are publicly available.

The cybersecurity-related text datasets mentioned in the dynamic approaches for taxonomies are the Cyber Security Dataset [4], DNRTI [101], and APTNER [102]. The Cyber Security Dataset, presented in [4], includes 790 items and is based on a variety of sources, such as professional reports, academic papers, OSN data (Twitter timelines), and underground forum posts. To the best of our knowledge, the Cyber Security Dataset has not been made publicly available. The Dataset for Named Entity Recognition in Threat Intelligence (DNRTI) was compiled from more than 300 pieces of threat intelligence, it comprises 6,587 sentences (175,220 words), and was annotated by domain experts for the task of named entity recognition (NER). The provided annotation assigns the threat related terms (entities) to 13 cybersecurity-related categories (classes) following the BIO word boundary labelling scheme. DNRTI is publicly available [101]. APTNER, another dataset for NER in the cyberthreat intelligence field, was sourced from network security companies’ texts, contains more than 10,000 sentences, and was annotated to comply with STIX 2.1 standard. Its 21 classes were

defined in accordance with STIX 2.1, and the annotation of the entities follows the BIOES scheme. APTNER is also publicly available [102].

3.4.1 Scope and Limitations of the Datasets

Considering the data dependency of dynamic approaches for constructing cybersecurity taxonomies, it is appropriate to discuss some key issues exhibited by the datasets presented in this section:

- **Lack of Representativeness:** the three network flow datasets were explicitly designed around cybersecurity attacks, focusing primarily on network and DDoS attack scenarios. This introduces a scope limitation, as these datasets are representative only of attack-related behaviours and are insufficient for constructing broader taxonomies that include non-attack data (e.g., normal traffic patterns or defensive strategies) or other cybersecurity aspects. The NER datasets contain specifically annotated classes, meaning they can only cover the scope of those classes rather than the entire, constantly expanding cybersecurity domain.
- **Temporal Relevance:** The temporal context of the datasets presents a significant limitation. Both DARPA 2000 and CAIDA UCSD “DDoS Attack 2007” reflect the cybersecurity threats and network characteristics of their respective time periods (2000 and 2007). This introduces a temporal relevance issue, as these datasets cannot account for the evolution of attack techniques, traffic patterns, and modern network technologies, making them less applicable to current challenges.
- **Data Quality and Realism:** The quality and realism of the data in DARPA 2000 and CIC-DDoS2019 introduce some further considerations. These two datasets consist of synthetic data, which, despite efforts to make it realistic, may not fully capture the complexity of real-world environments, leading to potential ecological validity issues. Conversely, CAIDA UCSD “DDoS Attack 2007” includes real-world data but

is limited in duration (one hour) and anonymised to protect privacy. This anonymisation introduces a data obfuscation issue, which may limit the ability to analyse detailed interaction patterns and behaviours.

- **Class Imbalances:** DARPA 2000 exhibits underrepresentation of certain attack types relative to others, potentially skewing model training and evaluation. Similarly, CIC-DDoS2019 shows imbalances between attack traffic and normal traffic, which can lead to models biased toward over-detecting attack behaviours while reducing accuracy in identifying legitimate traffic. DNRTI also exhibits class imbalance, for example, the number of entities labelled as *HackOrg*, representing hacker organizations, is more than twice that of less frequent categories like *SecTeam*, which denotes security teams. And lastly, regarding APTNER, although it aims to represent 21 cybersecurity-related classes, it exhibits a severe class imbalance between its most frequent classes (e.g., *APT* for threat participants) and least frequent classes (e.g., *DOM*, *EMAIL*, *URL*, *VULID* for domain name, email, url, and vulnerability number, respectively). As a result, it is much less effective for tasks like NER for these underrepresented classes.

The Cyber Security Dataset [4] has not been made publicly available and therefore its contents cannot be verified or assessed. However, as it was compiled from texts from professional reports, academic papers, OSN data filtered by classifiers, and underground forum posts, potential issues include limited representativeness, biases from source selection, limited coverage of the field due to its static nature and size of 790 documents, and additionally the biases from machine learning classifiers performing the filtering.

Table 3 Datasets used in different approaches.

Dataset Name	Data Type	Date	Dataset Attributes	Applied Methods	Paper
2000 DARPA Intrusion Detection	Network Flows	07/2000	3 attacks scenarios: 2 attacks, 1 day's traffic + 1 attack 1 hour	-	[77]
CAIDA UCSD DDoS Attack 2007	Network Flows	04/08/2007		-	[77]
CIC-DDoS2019	Network Flows	2019	19 attacks across 13 classes, 5 h 39 min	ID3, Random Forest, Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression	[77]
CIC-DDoS2019	Network Flows	2019	19 attacks across 13 classes, 5 h 39 min	Decision Trees, Random Forest, ANN	[73]
Cyber Security Dataset	Texts	2019	790 items	Document Count, NLP: n-grams Extraction, TF-IDF	[4]
DNRTI	Texts	2020	> 300 CTI texts, 13 classes	NER, Regular Expressions	[101]
APTNER	Texts	2022	21 classes	-	[102]

Datasets used in different approaches.

3.5 Advantages and Drawbacks of dynamic taxonomies compared to manual taxonomies

Cybersecurity threats rapidly evolve, continuously introducing new variations, affecting organisations, critical infrastructures, and individuals. Given the extreme number of attacks presented every day as well as the automation of attacks, it is evident that the utilisation of automated procedures in cybersecurity is paramount towards addressing the evolving landscape of cyber threats. Automation in cybersecurity has been shown to offer several benefits, including enhancing cybersecurity defence policies [103, 104]. Taxonomies can enhance cybersecurity methods, and as such automation in the construction phase of the taxonomy is also crucial [4].

Different AI techniques such as NER can assist towards this way by automatically identifying cybersecurity terms. However, despite the automation offered by AI tools major drawbacks exist. Initially, AI methods may introduce noise by identifying terms that are not explicitly related to the cybersecurity domain. In addition, AI models are as good in identifying terms as the amount and diversity of data that have been trained. These reasons lead to the construction of incomplete cybersecurity taxonomies. To this end, human expertise and decision-making play an important role in the construction and evaluation of high-quality taxonomies.

In this scope, automated dynamic taxonomies are expected to provide several key benefits compared to conventional taxonomies [105, 106]. Despite the existence of research efforts for generating (semi-)automatic cybersecurity taxonomies and ontologies, many studies still rely on manual methods, requiring domain expertise from human experts [11].

3.5.1 Advantages

Similar to other automated approaches, automated taxonomies also offer several interrelated advantages.

Efficiency

As the growing variety and frequency of cyber-incidents may render conventional manually-created taxonomies ineffective, automation becomes essential. As security data volume increases, automated taxonomies provide efficiency in organisation and classification. This can mean better optimisation (i.e. higher precision, accuracy, etc.), reduced costs, and speed, further analysed below. Leveraging various automation methods, including AI or ML, to process vast amounts of data can ensure accurate and efficient threat identification, thereby strengthening defences against new attack vectors [77, 105–107].

Speed

Automation is also essential for swiftly managing and analysing data. Utilising automated taxonomy approaches can contribute to the intelligent processing of large volumes of data flow, facilitating the timely identification of emerging threats. This real-time analysis ensures quick and, by extension effective, responses to cyber-risks [77, 105–107].

Scalability

With the continuous influx of security alerts, the scalability of automated solutions is essential for the handling of diverse data attributes for classification. Automation facilitates the efficient processing and management of extensive data volumes, while scalability ensures the system's adaptability to emerging and evolving threats. Collectively, these attributes strengthen systemic resilience, enhance threat detection capabilities, and uphold the availability and functionality of the cybersecurity infrastructure. [105, 107].

Adaptability

ML-based solutions for cybersecurity taxonomies automate attack detection and can potentially evolve continuously, benefiting from features like recency mining and incremental learning to achieve dynamism. These processes ensure that security models remain up-to-date and adaptable to new threats in dynamic environments where behaviour is constantly evolving [105–107].

3.5.2 Drawbacks and Remediation Solutions

Despite the value of automation and the technical sophistication exhibited by automated taxonomies, they also present some inherent challenges.

Data Dependency

The effectiveness of automated taxonomies is limited by their data dependency. Automated models, such as machine learning-based models, heavily rely on extensive training datasets, hindering their generalisability to other datasets and applications. This reliance on data poses a significant challenge in cybersecurity, as obtaining and processing the necessary input samples for automated system development can be time-consuming and resource-intensive. Thus, while automated taxonomies offer valuable insights, their dependence on data, in terms of both quantity and quality, remains a notable disadvantage [77, 105, 106].

To mitigate the constraints that arise from the issue of data dependence different techniques can be used. Synthetic data generation can offer an advanced solution. The datasets that are artificially created with techniques such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), and LLMs address data scarcity, providing a viable alternative to acquiring large volumes of real data [108]. In addition, regarding data scarcity, few-shot learning techniques can also provide advanced solutions by enabling learning from a limited number of examples. These techniques can enable models to quickly adapt to new data, improving their generalisability [109].

Last transfer learning techniques can also help in the data dependence issue. With this technique models trained on a vast amount of data can be fine-tuned to be used in various scenarios reducing the need for extensive data collection and preprocessing [110].

Lack of Contextual Understanding

Current cybersecurity is highly dependent on analysing cyber data using data mining and machine learning, often missing vital contextual details like temporal and spatial relationships. Thus, while classification systems often prioritise (encoded) technical aspects alone this can lead to oversimplified frameworks that risk overlooking nuanced contextual information. This poses a significant limitation, revealing the need for context-aware adaptive solutions [47, 106].

For example, domain-specific NLP techniques can include knowledge focused on a particular domain (e.g. cybersecurity) to capture the domain's nuance better. For example, CySecBERT, a domain-adapted language model for cybersecurity, has been developed to improve the contextual understanding of cybersecurity data [111]. The contextual embeddings generated by these models can capture the semantics relationships between different entities enhancing the ability of models to recognize and classify complex patterns. An additional technique that can assist in providing contextual understanding is Knowledge Graphs (KGs). This technique includes entities related to a specific domain but also the relations between them, i.e. how 2 entities or more are related to each other. KGs are able to represent complex relationships between entities, providing a richer contextual understanding of cybersecurity data [112].

While there is no relevant literature concerning quantifiable metrics or case studies comparing dynamic and manual taxonomies, there are different quantifiable metrics which can be leveraged in terms of evaluating the quality of both manual and dynamic taxonomies as presented in 4. The scarcity of related research in the literature led to the

comparison of dynamic and manual taxonomies according to assumptions based on the characteristics outlined in the previous sections, while also considering the qualitative metrics. In this regard, both dynamic and manual taxonomies are considered to have various advantages and limitations when compared to each other. Specifically, dynamic taxonomies may have the potential to attain lower complexity measures; however, their strength may be weakened by the imprecise parameters influencing them. On the other hand, manual taxonomies are most likely to show higher levels of usability while being much less robust than dynamic taxonomies.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

The conducted research points out a noticeable absence of dynamic cybersecurity taxonomies and effective methods for constructing them. In particular, 91.1% of the studies in the literature address manual taxonomies, while only 8.9% study dynamic taxonomy approaches. This gap hinders the adaptability and responsiveness of cybersecurity measures in the rapidly evolving threat landscape.

Furthermore, the findings of this research set out actionable strategies that business leaders and policymakers can take advantage of to realise advanced cybersecurity innovation. The reduction of operational costs, adherence to regulatory frameworks, and promotion of synergistic public-private partnerships collectively highlight the wider relevance of the work for addressing the compelling challenges facing modern cybersecurity.

With regard to other similar works, all the examined review studies include only manual taxonomies, and to the best of our knowledge, no existing research focuses on or explicitly mentions dynamic taxonomies. Our study, which centres specifically on cybersecurity threats, provides a detailed classification of existing manual cyberthreat taxonomies based on two key criteria: i) the methodology employed for taxonomy creation, distinguishing between manual and dynamic approaches, and ii) for the manual

Table 4 Quantifiable metrics.

Metric	Description
Complexity (includes Preparation extensiveness, The difficulty of creation, description and understanding, and required resources in terms of Cost, Number of analysts, Effort and Expertise)	Evaluate the complexity in the taxonomy construction and usage [113].
Usability (includes Ease of Use, Efficiency, Universality, Satisfaction, Learnability, Effectiveness and Usefulness metrics)	Measures the general usability of a constructed taxonomy. [113].
Acceptance (includes Perceived Usefulness and Effort Expectancy metrics and quality metrics such as Completeness, Accuracy, Level of Detail, Scope Width)	Evaluate the extent to which the constructed taxonomy captures its initial purpose of construction [113].
Discoverability	Measures how fast and easily a threat vulnerability can be detected and added to the taxonomy [114].
Comprehensiveness	Refers to the ability of the taxonomy to classify all known objects within the intended domain [115].
Reliability	Assesses classification consistency [115].
Robustness	Measures the amount of misclassified objects [115].
Mutual Exclusiveness	Measures ambiguous objects classified into different categories [115].
Conciseness	Measure the unused objects of a taxonomy [115].
Extensibility	Measures the number of modifications required when new objects are added [115].

Quantifiable metrics of cybersecurity taxonomies.

taxonomies, the specific domain targeted by the proposed taxonomy (e.g., the CIA triad, cyber kill chain, domain, functionality, etc.). While this focused examination of cybersecurity threats provides useful insights, it also introduces certain limitations. Notably, our study excludes a range of cybersecurity-related works that focus on topics such as cybercrime and cybersecurity education and training.

The development and implementation of (semi-)automated approaches towards the creation of dynamic taxonomies in the cybersecurity domain hold significant potential for enhancing the management and mitigation of cyber threats. While dynamic taxonomies offer significant advantages in terms of efficiency, speed, scalability, and adaptability, their current limitations, such as data dependency, lack of contextual understanding. Despite the clear need, there is a notable lack of dynamic taxonomies in the field. This deficit stems from the limited methods for creating automated and adaptable taxonomies. Therefore, further research for the creation of dynamic taxonomies is required to capitalise on their potential as valuable tools against cyber threats.

Understanding the limited adoption of (semi-)automated approaches for dynamic cybersecurity taxonomies involves examining a range of potential factors. Existing literature and observed patterns suggest several possible reasons:

- Complexity of the cybersecurity domain; complex relationships between threats, vulnerabilities, attack methods, and mitigation strategies. Capturing interrelations accurately requires deep domain knowledge.
- Need for high-quality, labelled data to train ML models. Such data are for the most part not available [116], at least up until now (the creation of synthetic data may contribute to progress in this aspect).
- Although state-of-the-art NLP techniques can facilitate the understanding and extraction of information in cybersecurity in the form of textual reports, advisories, and logs, these texts also often require more sophisticated, tailored NLP approaches that can handle jargon, abbreviations, context-specific meaning, and neologisms [117].
- As taxonomies can potentially be used in the scope of critical applications, human experts need to trust and understand automated taxonomies; this commands the application of Explainable AI (XAI) [118].

- Expert knowledge is still required to understand nuances and subtle differences between terms and concepts.

Given the above, concerning future work in the domain of the dynamic cybersecurity taxonomies creation, potential solutions are anticipated to leverage advanced ML and NLP techniques, including LLMs [119] and their applications, as well as related knowledge representation approaches such as KGs [112]. More specifically, ML and NLP techniques hold the potential for enhancing pattern and entity recognition, and classification of entities intended for inclusion in cybersecurity taxonomies. Specialised LLMs can interpret complex cybersecurity terminology, thereby enhancing the accuracy and utility of extracted information. They can also be utilised in synthetic data generation. KGs can provide a foundational framework for structuring and representing intricate interrelationships and entities, thereby facilitating the construction of cybersecurity taxonomies. They constitute a useful approach for facilitating semantic understanding and integrating diverse data sources [120]. Lastly, human expertise remains a paramount asset for interpreting nuanced contextual factors, validating the insights generated by automated systems, and ensuring the relevance and applicability of cybersecurity taxonomies in real-world scenarios.

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Author contribution

All authors contributed equally to the study's conception and design. The design and preparation of the research methodology were performed by Eleni Darra and Arnlnt Spyros. Material preparation, data collection and analysis were performed by Anna Kougioumtzidou and Aggelos Papoutsis. Athanasios Tziouvaras and Dimitrios Kavalieros performed the review and editing while Theodora Tsikrika, Stefanos Vrochidis and Ioannis Kompatsiaris supervised the overall work. The first draft of the manuscript was written by all the authors with equal contributions in the different sections of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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